

Reaching agreement on priorities for the Global Plastics Treaty: The role of independent science in helping negotiators find common ground

Regular and meaningful opportunities for independent scientific input to global plastics treaty (GPT) negotiations and subsequent implementation is critical to support member states in making science-based decisions, to agree upon common priorities, and to ensure the treaty is comprehensive, credible, just, and effective in delivering UNEA 5/14.¹⁻²

The essential role of scientific input in supporting informed decision-making is widely recognised in Multilateral Environmental Agreements (MEAs).³⁻⁵ While other MEAs have benefited from diverse independent expert contributions, there are currently no individual or collective MEAs nor associated subsidiary or scientific bodies that can address the full plastics life cycle and effectively end plastic pollution (See Table 1 in [our policy brief](#) on releases and leakages).

Delivering the ambition mandated by UNEA 5/14 will require independent evidence spanning the full life cycle of plastics including feedstock extraction, product design and innovation, as well as consumption, waste management, pollution prevention, and safe and sustainable removal of legacy plastics. This evidence will be essential to 1) ensure that concepts and definitions are supported by robust science and are applied consistently across GPT articles; 2) help negotiators find much needed common ground on which to build an effective treaty; 3) identify additional data requirements for effective implementation and; 4) develop monitoring approaches to evaluate progress against the goals of the treaty.

Member states regularly request greater access to independent scientific guidance, yet opportunities to engage directly with scientists are becoming increasingly limited. This is delaying progress toward finding common goals within the negotiations. Moreover, the growing presence of actors with commercial conflicts of interests is further polarizing opinions.⁶ We summarise below (Table 1) some examples of how independent scientific knowledge can help identify practical pathways to advance negotiations.

Are you a negotiator looking for scientific evidence or support related to the Plastics Treaty? Please contact us via secretariat@scientistscoalition.org to set up a confidential meeting.

Table 1. How independent scientific evidence can support negotiations relative to articles of the Chair’s Text, December 2024⁷

Examples of where independent scientific evidence can support negotiation and implementation	Examples of relevant evidence reviews
<p>2 Definitions - Unambiguous definitions are fundamental for harmonized implementation</p>	<p>Comments on Article 2: Definitions</p>
<p>3 Plastic Products, 4 Exemptions, and 5 Plastic Product Design - Information on safer and more sustainable product design including plastic chemicals of concern and microplastics are needed to guide the compilation and regular review and updating of product</p>	<p>Benefits of regulating chemicals of concern</p> <p>Plastic Chemicals</p>

Examples of where independent scientific evidence can support negotiation and implementation	Examples of relevant evidence reviews
<p>listings in treaty annexes, including exemptions. Evidence on potential for safe and sustainable re-use/refill, recyclability, alternatives and substitutes (including biodegradable and compostable plastics), durability and many other features will be key to guiding product and system innovation and avoiding regrettable substitutions. Guidance on appropriate monitoring approaches will also be key in assessing effectiveness of the treaty.</p>	<p>Microplastic Pollution</p> <p>Impacts of plastics across the food system</p> <p>Safer and more sustainable product design</p> <p>Bio-based plastic, biodegradable plastic & bioplastic</p> <p>Essential use concept & time bound exemptions</p> <p>Monitoring Plastic Pollution</p>
<p>6 [Supply] [Sustainable Production] - Evidence-based policy frameworks and accurate data, including economic data, will ensure that only plastic products which bring essential benefits to society are produced. Evidence-based policy frameworks and accurate data will be needed to guide supply side measures, safe and sustainable trade, and support future sustainable innovation.</p>	<p>Achieving a primary plastic production target</p> <p>Upstream reduction of primary plastic polymers</p> <p>Cutting Plastic Pollution at the Source</p>
<p>7 Releases and Leakages - Information on emissions, releases, and leakage to the environment will be essential to guide monitoring, use and handling, prevention and minimisation interventions, and product design to minimise the risk of regrettable substitution. Guidance on appropriate monitoring approaches will also be key in assessing effectiveness of the treaty.</p>	<p>Releases and leakages across the lifecycle of plastics</p> <p>Monitoring Plastic Pollution</p>
<p>8 Plastic Waste Management - Information on plastic waste trade and waste management will be needed to reduce waste volumes and types, and improve waste management practices while also improving basic services for all. Guidance on appropriate safety, sustainability, transparency and monitoring standards and approaches will be key in assessing the effectiveness of the treaty.</p>	<p>Safer and more sustainable waste management</p> <p>Monitoring Plastic Pollution</p>
<p>9 Existing Plastic Pollution - Scientific assessment of the transparency, equity, safety and sustainability of legacy plastic pollution removal approaches will be key to minimising associated environmental, social, and economic impacts. Guidance on appropriate standards and monitoring approaches will also be key in assessing the effectiveness of the treaty.</p>	<p>Removal of existing and legacy plastic pollution</p> <p>Monitoring Plastic Pollution</p>

Examples of where independent scientific evidence can support negotiation and implementation	Examples of relevant evidence reviews
<p>10 Just Transition; 11 Financial [Resources and] Mechanism - Information on individuals, communities, nations, and regions that could be negatively impacted by measures addressing plastic pollution will be essential to guide appropriate financing of the treaty and assist in finding common ground on the instrument.</p>	<p>A just transition away from plastic pollution</p>
<p>12 Capacity Building Technical Assistance and Technology Transfer, Including International Cooperation - Identifying technology and infrastructure needs of member states, for example to test products for compliance in relation to chemicals of concern, or to establish monitoring protocols including for transboundary pollution, will be essential to build confidence in and agreement on the instrument.</p>	<p>A just transition away from plastic pollution</p>
<p>13 Implementation and Compliance; 14 National Plans; 15 Reporting; 16 Effectiveness Evaluation - Identifying approaches to test, monitor, and report on effectiveness at multiple scales of governance will be essential to ensure the treaty delivers against its objectives to end plastic pollution.</p>	<p>Monitoring Plastic Pollution</p>
<p>17 Information Exchange - Ensuring appropriate independent evidence to guide agreement on, and implementation of, the Articles listed above will require synthesis, evaluation and communication of complex information in readily accessible formats and in multiple languages.</p>	<p>Towards an Effective Science-Policy Interface for the Global Plastics Treaty</p>
<p>18 Public Information, awareness, education and research - Science contributions, including from environmental, behaviour change and communication studies, will inform the synthesis, evaluation, and communication of complex information in publicly accessible formats and multiple languages needed for treaty effectiveness.</p>	<p>Towards an Effective Science-Policy Interface for the Global Plastics Treaty</p>
<p>19 Health - Taking a One Health approach to understanding the risks of plastic pollution to human and environmental health is a key enabler for the treaty negotiations and effective implementation. Safe and sustainable product design will require a One Health approach ensuring materials protect human and environmental health. Robust independent scientific evidence will be needed to support informed decision-making, build confidence, and facilitate safe and effective outcomes for future generations.</p>	<p>Health impacts of plastic pollution along the full life cycle of plastics</p> <p>Plastics and the Triple Planetary Crisis</p> <p>Scientists' Coalition declaration on the One Health impacts of plastics</p>

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<p>20 bis Subsidiary Bodies - The Chairs' Text makes over 40 references to the need for scientific input and subsidiary bodies. Ensuring that independent scientists, who are free of conflict of interests, are enabled to participate in subsidiary bodies will be critical to a successful global plastics treaty.</p>	<p>Towards an Effective Science-Policy Interface for the Global Plastics Treaty</p>

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1 GRID-Arendal (2023). Science-policy interface for plastic pollution. GRID-Arendal. Arendal. Karen Raubenheimer, Niko Urho. <https://www.grida.no/publications/1007>.

2 International Science Council, 2023. Policy Brief: Creating a strong interface between science, policy and society to tackle global plastic pollution. <https://council.science/publications/policy-brief-tackle-global-plastic-pollution>.

3 UNEP (2020). Assessment of options for strengthening the science-policy interface at the international level for the sound management of chemicals and waste. UNEP: Nairobi, Kenya. ISBN No: 978-92-807-3840-7. <https://www.unep.org/resources/report/assessment-options-strengthening-science-policy-interface-international-level>.

4 Akhtar-Schuster (2022). Assessing the Impact of Science in the Implementation of the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11040568>.

5 Wang (2022). Enhancing scientific support for the Stockholm Convention's implementation: An analysis of policy needs for scientific evidence. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c06120>.

6 Fieber, R., Kaipainen, J., Markard, J., & Bening, C. (2026). Counter-intermediation strategies in transition policy-making: Exploration of the global plastics treaty negotiations. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 60, 101132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2026.101132>.

7 UNEP. (2024). Chair's Text - Fifth Session Busan. Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee to Develop an International Legally Binding Instrument on Plastic Pollution, Including in the Marine Environment. <https://wedocs.unep.org/handle/20.500.11822/46710>. Note: This version of the draft treaty text was selected because it represents the latest text accepted by the intergovernmental negotiating committee (INC) as the basis for further negotiations. It also contains key elements reflected in subsequent versions.